

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Family functioning, family relationship problems, and psychological wellbeing among young adults

Archana S * and Anjana Sinha

Department of Psychology, Kristu Jayanti College (Autonomous), K. Narayanapura, Kothanur (PO), Bengaluru 560077, India.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 22(01), 637–647

Publication history: Received on 01 March 2024; revised on 09 April 2024; accepted on 11 April 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.22.1.1107>

Abstract

The study aims to examine the relationship between family functioning, family relationship problems, and psychological well-being among young adults in the southern region of India. The data was collected from a total 265 young adults aged 18 – 26 years old, through both online and offline means i.e. hybrid method was used. Using a quantitative non-experimental design, employing correlation analysis, data was analyzed. The measures that were used in the study were Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scale (FACES III), the Index of Family Relations (IFR), and Ryff's Psychological Well-being Scale (PWB) – 42items. The finding of the study show that there was indeed a significant relationship between family cohesion, a subdomain in family functioning and the domains of psychological wellbeing. However, no significant relationship was observed between family adaptability, another subdomain in family functioning and the domains psychological well-being. Conversely, family relationship problems showed a significant negative correlation with various aspects of psychological well-being, indicating that higher levels of family conflict were associated with lower levels of psychological well-being. In conclusion, the findings underscore the importance of addressing family dynamics and conflict resolution strategies to promote the psychological well-being of young adults.

Keywords: Family; Family functioning; Family relationship problems; Psychological wellbeing

1. Introduction

Family, as an integral component of human existence, plays a profound and important role in shaping individuals' lives across the lifespan. Family serves as a foundation of a person's psychological, emotional and social development. When adolescents go through the transition phase from adolescents to adults, they are faced with various challenges and responsibilities which are often intersected with their family.

Family is not just seen as a group of people living together but seen as something beyond that. Significant transformations, including the rise in divorce and in separation rates, increased instances of domestic violence, social issues such as drug abuse and juvenile delinquency and inter-generational conflicts are currently being experienced by families in India. These shifts suggest the challenges in managing the demands of contemporary life. However, a substantial portion of families are successful in demonstrating resilience, displaying the ability to evolve, accommodate, and adapt to evolving social norms, values, and structures. They have exhibited a remarkable capacity to remain cohesive and united despite the increasing pressures and stresses of modern life [20].

Family functioning is referred to the way a family operates with each other and interacts with each other. To be precise, family functioning can be characterized by the manner in which family members interact socially and structurally and it is demonstrated through how well the family is united, close, and effective in term communication within themselves

* Corresponding author: Archana S

[10]. According to the *Circumplex Model*, cohesion and adaptability both together comprise a family functioning. Each of these dimensions include four levels [13]. The four levels of cohesion are disengaged, separated, connected and enmeshed and the four levels of adaptability are rigid, structured, flexible and chaotic [11].

A study of Vandeleur et al. [23] in 2009, explored if high cohesion and satisfaction with family had relationship high emotional wellbeing. Data was collected by both the adolescents and their parents daily for a week using daily reports and self-administrated measures. According to the results, higher cohesion was associated with increased well-being in fathers and adolescents, but not in mothers [23].

Strained family connections are marked by disputes, perpetual criticism, and demanding expectations whereas a secure and nurturing family bonds offer affection, guidance, and caregiving [9]. These aspects play a very important role in shaping an individual's identity, self-esteem, and overall psychological health [21, 22]. Furthermore, as young adults strive to achieve autonomy and independence, the influence of family and its functioning on their psychological well-being becomes increasingly significant. The interaction of family members with each other can have long-lasting effects on a person's development and overall well-being through psychological, behavioral, and physiological mechanisms [15]. Therefore, the family relationships quality and the dynamics within a family can either promote or hinder a person's health [9].

It is common to have issues or problems in a family and is considered to be a part of family life. If it is short term, then it can resolve within no time. But when it gets severe, it can lead to disturbances, later on affecting members of the family negatively [1]. The long term exposure can cause psychological issues as well. With this, members of family may experience depressive symptoms, like feelings of lonely or sad, or isolating themselves for a longer period of time. In addition to this, it can also cause and increase anxiety.

A study by Şenormanci et al. [17] in 2014, talks about excessive and uncontrollable internet usage. And one of the important associating factor was found to be family relationship problems. Even the moderate levels of internet usage have been associated with disturbed family relationships. This study talks about the case reports which highlights the interplay between internet addiction and family relationship problems.

The study done by Mood et al. [12] in 2016, highlighted that mental health of children from immigrant backgrounds was significantly influenced by family. These children tend to have better mental health despite facing challenges. The important factors that play a crucial were found to be family cohesion and parental warmth, with family cohesion being particularly important.

According many research studies, members of the families with severe relationship problems have experienced distress, anxiety and other psychological issues. Hence, there's the need to look into the family relationship problems. In shaping an individual's identity, self-esteem, and overall psychological health, all these aspects play a pivotal role. Furthermore, as young adults strive to achieve autonomy and independence, the psychological well-being can be significantly increased by family relations and factors related to it [6, 7, 8].

Psychological wellbeing is a multi-dimensional construct which is encompassed of aspects of mental health which includes cognitive, emotional and social aspects [16, 19]. Numerous factors influence these factors, including but not limited to family. Psychological well-being, a six factor model, was developed by Carol Ryff [16, 19]. According to this model, there are few factors that influence an individual's psychological well-being and overall happiness [16, 19]. The new measures consists of *purpose in life* which refers to the feeling one can have that their life has a purpose and meaning, *autonomy* which refers to one achieving independence and self-determination, *environmental mastery* which refers to the feeling to have control of life situations and circumstances, *personal growth* which refers to growing as an individual by using one's resources and talents, *self-acceptance* refers to being apprehensive of one's knowledge and limitations, but also accepting oneself, lastly *positive relationships*, pertaining to the capability to maintain deep connections with significant people and have meaningful connections [16, 19]. These components of psychological well-being are interconnected, working in harmony to enhance overall satisfaction, happiness, and well-being in individuals' lives [3].

In 2023, a study by Sharma, Rani, and Singh [18] investigated how home environment, personality, and aggression can have an impact on adult well-being. In the findings, the studied highlighted that a supportive home environment is important for a positive psychological outcomes in adulthood. An increased stress and reduced mental health aspects were found in relation to exposure of aggression and negative family dynamics.

1.1. Need and significance of study

Understanding how family functioning, family relationship problems and psychological wellbeing interact with each other in the lives of young adults is essential during the transition of young adults from adolescents.

The study determines to focus on young adults as they go through the transition of adults from adolescents, as this phase is caught up by many challenges and tasks like autonomy, identify formation and building on interpersonal relationship, there is an extensive need to study how factors of family influence the mental health outcomes of young adults.

Also, although there are extensive research done on adolescents, the research done on young adults is apparently very less. Therefore, there is a pressing need for this study.

1.2. Research gap

The studies on young adults in the context of family and their psychological wellbeing were relatively less. Hence, understanding how aspects of family can be a factor in understanding psychological wellbeing of young adults is crucial, because during this developmental period the foundation for future mental health outcomes and social functioning is laid.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

Quantitative non-experimental study with the correlation approach.

2.2. Statement of the problem

Exploring the correlation among the functionality of family units, familial relationship problems, and the psychological wellbeing of young adults is crucial. The study aims to comprehend how these elements interact within the lives of individuals transitioning from adolescence to adulthood.

2.3. Objectives

- To explore and examine the relationship between family functioning and psychological wellbeing and it's subdomains among young adults
- To study is family relationship problems has any correlation with psychological wellbeing and it's subdomains among young adults

2.4. Hypothesis

- H_01 : There is no significant relationship between family functioning and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults
- H_02 : There is no significant relationship between family cohesion and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults
- H_03 : There is no significant relationship between family adaptability and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults
- H_04 : There is no significant relationship between family relationship problems and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults

2.5. Operational definitions of the variables

2.5.1. Family functioning

Family functioning refers the way a family operates and interacts with each other. The ability to adapt and the cohesion of a family can be referred to as family functioning.

2.5.2. Family relationship problems

Family relationship problems refer to conflicts, tensions, or difficulties that arise within the context of a family which include things like disagreements, breakdowns, distance or any unresolved conflicts which might effects the wellbeing of family and its members.

2.5.3. Psychological Well-Being

Psychological Well-Being is a multifaceted construct which comprises of various aspects of emotional, cognitive and social functioning of an individual.

2.5.4. Young adults

This age group typically encompasses of transition from adolescence to adulthood where young adults have significant challenges in their physical, cognitive, emotional, and social lives.

2.5.5. Variables

Independent variables are family functioning and family relationship problems and dependent variable is psychological wellbeing

2.6. Demographic variables

Age, gender, family type and educational qualifications are the demographic details.

2.7. Universe of the study

Young adults from different family types who reside in southern part of India.

2.8. Sample Distribution

Table 1 The sample distribution

	N	265
Gender	Male	94
	Female	171
Family type	Nuclear	216
	Extended/joint	49

2.8.1. Inclusion criteria

- Young adults aged between 18-26 years
- Young adults who are educated and understand English.

2.8.2. Exclusion criteria

- Young adults who are orphans
- Individuals who have severe cognitive impairments or those unable to provide informed consent will be excluded from the study.

2.9. Sample and Techniques

The study employed a sample size of 265 subjects were employed for this study from the southern part of India. The sample comprises young adults aged between 18 to 26, due to their crucial identity-forming phase. Also, due to the lack of study on this population. Convenient sampling is chosen for selection of participants.

2.10. Research Ethics Followed

An overview of the study was provided to the participants before the handing out the questionnaires. They were explained about their role and its importance. Additionally, confidentiality and informed consent were discussed as well.

2.11. Tools for the study

The study used the Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scale (FACES III; Olson et al., 1985) to assess family functioning, Index of family relations (IFR) to assess family relationship problems and Ryff's Psychological wellbeing Scale (PWB) – 42 items scale to assess psychological wellbeing.

2.12. Statistical analysis

The study used correlational analysis to understand the relationship between the variables of the study. The data of the present study was not normally distributed, hence spearman rho correlation was used.

2.13. Descriptive and inferential statistics

To summarise characteristics of the sample of the study, descriptive statistics were used. Inferential statistics was used to analyse relationships and make predictions about the broader population.

3. Results and Discussion

The present study aimed to study relationship of family functioning, family relationship problems and psychological wellbeing among young adults. The study involved a total of 265 young adults aged between 18-26 years old from southern part of India. It was found that the data was not normally distributed. Hence, Spearman's rho correlation was used to check the correlation between the variables, which the study aims for.

Table 2 Sample characteristics

Sample characteristics		N	%
Gender	Female	171	64.50%
	Male	94	35.50%
Age	18	44	16.60%
	19	42	15.80%
	20	49	18.50%
	21	38	14.30%
	22	36	13.60%
	23	29	10.90%
	24	14	5.30%
	25	5	1.90%
	26	8	3.00%
	Educational qualification	10th	1
12th		16	6.00%
Under graduation		194	73.20%
Post-graduation		54	20.40%
Family type	Extended/joint	49	18.50%
	Nuclear	216	81.50%

The above table provides an overview of the sample characteristics of the participants. Firstly talking about the gender distribution, females have been found to be the majority of participants with 64.50% of the sample, and males are of 35.50%. Coming to the age distribution, it ranged from 18 to 26 years, where the highest representation was 20- and 21-year-old categories. Coming to educational qualifications, under graduation students were found to be the majority of participants with 73.20%, followed by post-graduation with 20.40%, and then 12th grade with 6.00% followed by SSLC of 0.40%. Coming to the Family type, majority of the participants belonged to nuclear family structures with 81.50% of the sample, and the remaining belonged to extended or joint family structures.

Table 3 The descriptive statistics

N = 265	Mean	Std. Deviation
Family functioning	61.483	12.16337
Family cohesion	33.92	7.173
Family adaptability	27.57	6.602
Family relationship problem	51.49	28.382
Autonomy	31.40	6.223
Environmental mastery	30.05	5.807
Personal growth	32.69	6.672
Positive relations	26.90	5.991
Purpose in life	31.23	6.257
Self-acceptance	30.93	6.500

The table above shows the descriptive statistics, based on a sample size of 265 respondents. Among these dimensions, Family functioning has a mean score of 61.483 and standard deviation score of 12.16337. Family cohesion the mean score was found to be 33.92 and standard deviation was 7.173, which indicates a moderate level of perceived family cohesion within the sample. Additionally, the Family Adaptability dimension showcases a lower mean score of 27.57, suggesting comparatively less adaptability within family functioning. Family Relationship Problems demonstrates a higher mean score of 51.49. On an individual level, autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, purpose in life, Positive Relations and Self-Acceptance mean scores were found to be 31.40, 30.05, 32.69, 26.90, 31.23 and 30.93 respectively and standard score of the same was found to be 6.223, 5.807, 6.672, 5.991, 6.257 and 6.500 respectively.

Table 4 The correlation coefficients between Family functioning and subdomains of psychological wellbeing

	N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Family functioning	265	1						
Autonomy	265	0.035	1					
Environmental mastery	265	0.163**	0.381**	1				
Personal growth	265	0.011	0.377**	0.527**	1			
Positive relations	265	0.109	0.191**	0.426**	0.502**	1		
Purpose in life	265	0.076	0.303**	0.409**	0.524**	0.361**	1	
Self-acceptance	265	0.170**	0.420**	0.472**	0.385**	0.417**	0.405**	1

Note: **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above results reveals the relationship between Family Functioning and various subdomains of psychological well-being among individuals. It was found that there is statistically significant correlations between Family Functioning and three specific subdomains of psychological wellbeing: Environmental Mastery, Positive Relations, and Self-acceptance. Family functioning had a moderately positive correlation with Environmental Mastery ($r = 0.163$, $p < 0.01$), Positive Relations ($r = 0.109$, $p < 0.01$) and Self-Acceptance ($r = 0.170$, $p < 0.01$), indicating that individuals who perceive higher levels of functioning within their families tend to also report greater environmental mastery, positive relations and self-acceptance. However, there was no statistically significant correlations between Family Functioning and the subdomains of Autonomy, Personal Growth, and Purpose in Life. These findings underscore the nuanced relationship between family functioning and psychological well-being, suggesting that while few aspects of family functioning may strongly influence specific dimensions of well-being, others may have less pronounced effects. Although, the results show that only certain domains of psychological wellbeing and family functioning have a significant relationship, we can still reject the null hypothesis "there is no significant relationship between family functioning and psychological

wellbeing among young adults”, as family functioning still has a relationship with few subdomains of psychological wellbeing.

Table 5 The correlation coefficients between Family cohesion and subdomains of psychological wellbeing

	N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Family cohesion	265	1						
Autonomy	265	0.082	1					
Environmental mastery	265	0.208**	0.381**	1				
Personal growth	265	0.114	0.377**	0.527**	1			
Positive relations	265	0.187**	0.191**	0.426**	0.502**	1		
Purpose in life	265	0.175**	0.303**	0.409**	0.524**	0.361**	1	
Self-acceptance	265	0.253**	0.420**	0.472**	0.385**	0.417**	.0405**	1

Note: **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table shows the correlation between Family cohesion and subdomains of psychological wellbeing. Each of these coefficients represents the direction and strength of relationship between Family cohesion and specific domains of psychological wellbeing. The results reveal that Autonomy and Family cohesion have a weak positive correlation where, $r = 0.082$, which indicates that there is a slight relationship between Family cohesion and Autonomy. Then coming to Environmental Mastery and Family cohesion, a moderate positive correlation was observed with $r = 0.208$. This means that people who tend to report higher levels of family cohesion show higher level of Environmental Mastery. Personal Growth and Family cohesion showed a weak positive correlation with $r = 0.114$, meaning that there is a slight association between family cohesion and Personal Growth. Coming to Positive Relations and Family cohesion, a moderate positive correlation was found with $r = 0.187$, meaning people who tend to report higher levels of family cohesion show higher level of Positive Relations. Then coming to Purpose in Life and Family cohesion, a moderate positive correlation was found where $r = 0.175$. This indicates that those who have strong sense of purpose tend to report higher levels of family cohesion, Lastly, Self-Acceptance and Family cohesion demonstrated a moderate positive correlation where $r = 0.253$, meaning higher levels of family cohesion is linked to higher levels of Self-Acceptance. Overall, it can be said that there is indeed a significant relationship between Family cohesion and the domains of psychological wellbeing i.e. Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance. Hence, the null hypothesis (Ho2) which states that “there is no significant relationship between family cohesion and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults” can be rejected.

Table 6 The correlation coefficients between Family adaptability and subdomains of psychological wellbeing

	N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Family adaptability	265	1						
Autonomy	265	0	1					
Environmental mastery	265	0.071	0.381**	1				
Personal growth	265	-0.09	0.377**	0.527**	1			
Positive relations	265	0.006	0.191**	0.426**	0.502**	1		
Purpose in life	265	-0.061	0.303**	0.409**	0.524**	0.361**	1	
Self-acceptance	265	0.059	0.420**	0.472**	0.385**	0.417**	0.405**	1

Note: **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 6 provides the correlation coefficients between Family Adaptability and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among the sample of 265 individuals. The results reveal that, Autonomy shows no significant correlation with Family Adaptability. This indicates that the extent to which individuals perceive autonomy in their lives is not linked to the adaptability of their family. Next, Environmental Mastery and Family Adaptability reveal a very weak positive correlation, which implies that there is a minimal tendency for people who reported high level of environmental mastery

have high family adaptability. Personal Growth and Family Adaptability shows a negative correlation which can be negligible. This suggests that a slight tendency for individuals in families with higher adaptability to report slightly lower levels of personal growth, though with minimal practical significance. Family Adaptability several a weak correlations with Positive Relations, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance, which indicates a limited connection between family adaptability and these aspects of psychological wellbeing. Although, due to the large sample, significance is observed in few correlations, the practical relevance of the same seems to be limited, which implies that Family Adaptability and psychological well-being subdomains may have a statistical association, but might not have substantial practical implications or meaningful impact in real-life contexts. Hence, the null hypothesis (Ho3) which “there is no significant relationship between family adaptability and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults” can be accepted because the results of significant correlation fall between negligible to weak.

Table 7 The correlation coefficients between Family relationship problems and subdomains of psychological wellbeing

	N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Family relationship problem	265	1						
Autonomy	265	-0.191**	1					
Environmental mastery	265	-0.352**	0.381**	1				
Personal growth	265	-0.259**	0.377**	0.527**	1			
Positive relations	265	-0.378**	0.191**	0.426**	0.502**	1		
Purpose in life	265	-0.227**	0.303**	0.409**	0.524**	0.361**	1	
Self-acceptance	265	-0.365**	0.420**	0.472**	0.385**	0.417**	0.405**	1

Note: **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table 7 shows the results of correlation coefficients between Family relationship problems and the subdomains of psychological wellbeing. The results show that there is a moderately negative correlation ($r = -0.191$, $p < 0.01$) between Family relationship problems and Autonomy. There is a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.352$, $p < 0.01$) between Family relationship problems and Environmental Mastery. Coming to Personal growth, there is a moderately negative correlation ($r = -0.259$, $p < 0.01$) with Family relationship problems. Between Positive relations and Family relationship problems, there is a strongly negative correlation ($r = -0.378$, $p < 0.01$). Next, there is a moderately negative correlation ($r = -0.227$, $p < 0.01$) between Purpose in Life and Family Relationship Problems. Finally, Self-acceptance, has a strong negative correlation ($r = -0.365$, $p < 0.01$) with Family relationship problems. When we look at the results, it indicates family relationship problems increase, the levels of Psychological wellbeing decreases across all the subdomains. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho4) which states that “there is no significant relationship between family relationship problems and subdomains of psychological wellbeing among young adults” can be rejected.

4. Discussion

4.1. Family Functioning and Psychological Well-being

The results revealed that there was significant correlations between family functioning and few specific subdomains of psychological well-being. Family cohesion, although had varying results in terms of relationship with subdomains of psychological well-being, it can be said that there was indeed a significant relationship between family cohesion and psychological wellbeing. Higher levels of family cohesion were associated with higher levels of Autonomy, Environmental Mastery, Personal Growth, Positive Relations, Purpose in Life, and Self-Acceptance. These findings support a meta- analysis done by Amato and Keith [2] in 1991, which showcased the long term effects of family dynamics on psychological health. In addition to this, there was another research with which these findings align, which the research was done by Farajzadegan et al. [4] in 2013, highlighting the important role of family functioning in the influence of psychological wellbeing. In contrast to the above findings, the relationship between family adaptability and psychological well-being revealed mixed results. Some of the subdomains had weak correlations with family adaptability domain, to be precise, with autonomy and environmental mastery, where the practical significance of these associations remain limited. This contrasting results may stem from the different dimensions being measured within each construct. Family adaptability focuses on the ability to adapt to changes whereas cohesion focuses on the bonding, closeness etc. It is possible that families which demonstrate good cohesiveness may have difficulty with adaptability. Moreover, the way individuals perceive adaptability within the family unit might differ as well. To conclude, in shaping

psychological well-being, family cohesion appears to play a significant role and the relationship between family adaptability and psychological wellbeing remains less clear. So, this mixed results suggest that the relationship between these variables, can be multifaceted and depending on the specific dimensions being studied, it may vary.

4.2. Family Relationship Problems and Psychological Well-being

The family relationship problems and psychological well-being results, highlight a significant negative correlation across various subdomains of psychological well-being. This finding aligns with previous research by Amato and Keith [2] in 1991, which was a meta-analysis depicting the long term effects of parental divorce on adult well-being. Additionally, Fomby and Cherlin [5] in 2007 conducted a research in which they found that children had poorer developmental outcomes, who are from families experiencing multiple structural changes, which indicates that there is a clear relationship between family instability and well-being. The current study adds on to these findings by depicting that family relationship problems, such as conflicts and tensions, have links with lower levels of autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance among young adults. The results obtained through this study underscores the critical importance of addressing family relationship problems in promoting psychological well-being among young adults. The study done by Sharma, Rani, and Singh [18] in 2023, which highlighted the adverse impact of negative family dynamics, such as aggression and stress, on mental health outcomes in adulthood, supports these findings. In addition to this, the study by Qian et al. [14] in 2022) highlighted the mediating role of family functioning in mitigating loneliness among college students, further underscoring the importance of healthy family relationships for psychological well-being.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study examines the relationship between family functioning, family relationship problems, and psychological well-being among young adults in the southern part of India. Family functioning which involves family cohesion as a subdomain had a positive correlation with the subdomain of psychological wellbeing, which indicate that family cohesiveness fosters psychological well-being. Whereas, the other subdomain of family functioning, family adaptability appeared to be less pronounced, as the correlations of it with psychological well-being were negligible across all the subdomains of psychological well-being. Furthermore, it was found that there was a significant negative correlation between family relationship problems and the subdomains of psychological well-being, which indicates that conflicts, tensions, and difficulties within the family context can detrimentally impact autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations, purpose in life, and self-acceptance among young adults. With this, the study highlights the importance of addressing the conflicts or problems with the family relationship in order to foster the psychological wellbeing of young adults.

Overall, the study's finding contribute to the understanding of family functioning, family relationship problems and psychological wellbeing and their relationship with one another. The study emphasizes on the need for intervention in addressing the family functioning and family relationship problems in order improve and enhance psychological wellbeing of young adults.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to all those who contributed to the completion of this research project.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to my research guide, Dr. Anjana Sinha, for her invaluable guidance, support, and encouragement throughout the duration of this study. Her expertise and insights have been instrumental in shaping the direction and methodology of our research.

I also deeply grateful to the participants who generously shared their time and experiences, without whom this study would not have been possible. Their willingness to participate and provide valuable data is greatly appreciated.

Lastly, I acknowledge the contributions of all the researchers and scholars whose work has paved the way for advancements in the field of psychology and inspired this study.

Thank you all for your support and contributions.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this research paper.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Alm S, Brolin Låftman S, Bohman H. Poor Family Relationships in Adolescence and the Risk of Premature Death: Findings from the Stockholm Birth Cohort Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019;16(10):1690.
- [2] Amato PR, Keith B. Parental Divorce and Adult Well-Being: A Meta-Analysis. *J Marriage Fam*. 1991;53(1):43–58.
- [3] Dhanabhakya M, Sarath M. Psychological Wellbeing: A systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Communication and Technology*. 2023;3(1):603-607.
- [4] Farajzadegan Z, Koosha P, Sufi GJ, Keshvari M. The relationship between family function and women's well-being. *Iran J Nurs Midwifery Res*. 2013;18(1):9–13.
- [5] Fomby P, Cherlin AJ. Family Instability and Child Well-Being. *Am Sociol Rev*. 2007;72(2):181–204.
- [6] Gilligan M, Sutor J, Nam S, Routh B, Rurka M, Con G. Family Networks and Psychological Well-Being in Midlife. *Soc Sci*. 2017;6(3):94.
- [7] Grevenstein D, Bluemke M, Schweitzer J, Raab CA. Better family relationships--higher well-being: The connection between relationship quality and health related resources. *sciencedirect*. 2019.
- [8] Gul N, Ghani N, Alvi SM, Kazmi F, Shah AA. FAMILY SYSTEM'S ROLE IN THE PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING OF THE CHILDREN. *Khyber Med Univ J*. 2017;9(1):29–32.
- [9] Jabbari B, Rouster AS. Family Dynamics. In: *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing. 2022.
- [10] Lewandowski AS, Palermo TM, Stinson J, Handley S, Chambers CT. Systematic Review of Family Functioning in Families of Children and Adolescents With Chronic Pain. *The Journal of Pain*. 2010 Nov;11(11):1027–38.
- [11] Masselam VS, Marcus RF, Stunkard CL. Parent-adolescent communication, family functioning, and school performance. *Adolescence*. 1990;25(99):725–737.
- [12] Mood C, Jonsson JO, Låftman SB. The Mental Health Advantage of Immigrant-Background Youth: The Role of Family Factors. *J Marriage Fam*. 2016;79(2):419–436.
- [13] Olson DH. Circumplex Model of Marital and Family Systems. *J Fam Ther*. 2000;22(2):144–167.
- [14] Qian L, Wang D, Jiang M, Wu W, Ni C. The Impact of Family Functioning on College Students' Loneliness: Chain-Mediating Effects of Core Self-Evaluation and Problematic Mobile Phone Use. *Front Psychol*. 2022;13:915697.
- [15] Repetti RL, Taylor SE, Seeman TE. Risky families: Family social environments and the mental and physical health of offspring. *Psychol Bull*. 2002;128(2):330–366.
- [16] Ryff CD. Psychological Well-Being Revisited: Advances in the Science and Practice of Eudaimonia. *Psychother Psychosom*. 2014;83(1):10–28.
- [17] Şenormancı Ö, Konkan R, Güçlü O, Şenormancı G. Aşırı İnternet Kullanımı Nedeniyle Aile İlişkileri Bozulmuş Olan İki İnternet Bağımlılığı Olgusu. *Nöro Psikiyatri Arş*. 2014.
- [18] Sharma G, Rani S, Singh K. Impact of Home Environment, Aggression, and Personality on an Adult's Well-being: A Systematic Review. *Res Gate*.
- [19] Six-factor model of psychological well-being. *Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia*. Retrieved October 18, 2023.
- [20] Sonawat R. (PDF) Understanding families in India: A reflection of societal changes [Internet]. *ResearchGate*. 2001. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/26360843_Understanding_families_in_India_A_reflection_of_societal_changes
- [21] Thomas PA, Liu H, Umberson D. Family Relationships and Well-Being. *Innov Aging*. 2017;1(3):1–11.

- [22] Tramonti F, Petrozzi A, Burgalassi A, Milanfranchi A, Socci C, Belviso C, Mainardi C, Albanesi G, Guglielmi P. Family functioning and psychological distress in a sample of mental health outpatients: Implications for routine examination and screening. *J Eval*
- [23] Vandeleur CL, Jeanpretre N, Perrez M, Schoebi D. Cohesion, Satisfaction With Family Bonds, and Emotional Well-Being in Families With Adolescents. *J Marriage Fam.* 2009;71(5):1205-1219.